

CUSTOMER SHOPPING PATTERN PREDICTION USING RNN (RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORK)

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Abstract

Customer relationship management is very important in making marketing decisions large amounts of customer transaction data in Point of Sales systems are helpful in predicting customer behavior. However, there are no better modelling methods to perform analysis on such large sets of data. Neural Networks are helpful in making better decisions for providing better marketing strategic plans. Large corporations should have huge quantities of data available to them to predict the possible potential purchasing behavior for many of their clients. That way they can make timely decisions about stocking their shelves, providing customer recommendations on items, customer promotions, and predicting when a customer is losing interest in their service and planning to buy from a competitor. This research proposes an experiment on a consumer behavior prediction model of buying products, utilizing recurrent neural networks (RNNs), focusing on client loyalty number, recency, frequency, monetary value, and introducing a novel variable termed clumpiness. According to the experimental evidence it was obtained that the RNN predicts RFMC for customers more efficiently and accurately than convectional RFM for the same cases. Recommendation systems can eventually use this model for target marketing in different segments. We provide a modelling strategy that can help to predict customers' future long-term purchasing.

INTRODUCTION

Customer relationship management are the efforts of a company to manage interaction with all types of customers. One of the techniques to cope with this provocation is using consumer lifetime value (CLV) inspection. Consumer Lifetime Value (CLV) assists in

figuring out ideal customers that will bring the most potential at generating revenue. By having ample information about what the identified best customer's desire, target markets can be specified.

As gaining a new customer is more difficult than keeping current customers, the CLV focuses on improving long-term relationship with the customers. This is usually done by segmenting the customers based on their potential and loyalty. Then, marketing decision makers communicate with customers through methods targeted ads, attractive offers, and schemes to make the customer attracted to the company's offerings. Various techniques to capture customer purchasing patterns are defined by customer lifetime value analysis. Previous studies claim that one of the traditional and most reliable ones which marketing managers depend on, is utilizing the recency, frequency, and monetary value analysis which is also called RFM analysis. The RFM value give some understanding of customer behavior. Recency means last time the customer made a purchase; frequency means how much has been purchasing worth for a particular period, and monetary means the money spent for that period. We then introduce a new variable called clumpiness. Clumpiness of a customer basically means a burst period of buying. An example can make this distinction clear: if you bought orange juice and soap daily, you would be buying things in a regular pattern. But purchasing also displays clumpiness-the fact that customer buy in bursts or in an irregular pattern. And those burst buying intervals indicate uniqueness about a customer and that those customers could be extremely valuable. Out-of-sample clumpier customers yield more, and so does their value in the future. Therefore, another variable that companies should look for among their customers is clumpiness and use it in predicting the customer's worth in the future.

Ease of Use

Literature Review

Studies before expanded the possibilities of RFM analysis using advanced deep learning techniques (RNN) [1]. Also, they incorporated analysis and prediction of customer behavior using data mining and clickstream data [2]. Some of researchers have predicted the behavior from payment datasets [3]. Unfortunately, this method does not give much information about the customers. Revenue prediction by mining frequent item sets with customers [4] had been also analysis the pattern, they have used FM (frequency and monetary) value to analysis. Loraine

Chalet, A., & Kumar, A. employed the Market Basket Analysis technique to determine goods placement and devise sales promotions for various people visiting the market [6]. This analysis faces problem using frequent item sets mining, the item sets are obtained from database using K-Apriori algorithm and associated rules. [5] Eugene Wong forecasted client behaviors from clickstream data by sequence classification, as analyzed by Xing et al. [7], categorizing it into feature-based, sequence distance-based, and model-based methodologies. We do not mine data from the web. Deep learning methods are very appropriate and practical for modelling time-series data specially RNN model. According to Wharton marketing Professor Eric Bradlow, the consumer value measure for years has been RFM (recency, frequency and monetary value). In his view RFM is not complete characterization. One more variable is needed called "C" stands for clumpiness. He explains that concept based on a research paper titled "New Measures of Clumpiness for Incidence Data [8], to the best of our knowledge. In [9], Clickstream data from real shopping sessions served as the source of data for two machine learning techniques used to anticipate shoppers' behavior in advance. It employed a combination of RNN and Hidden Markov Models to examine the behavior of the shoppers. RNN was also used to predict customer behavior on Twitter [12]. In that work, thousands of tweets were analyzed and fed to an FF neural network to predict their relevance about purchasing behavior. Then an LSTM model was used in the actual purchase prediction. Hotel selection or preference in a city was also predicted using neural networks [13] This model utilizes a customer's historical data, including social media location check-ins, and the model is driven from the customer's mobility traits as inputs together with the effect of their social network. The use of big data and finding segments from huge quantities of POS data along with RFM variables to reduce the data for analysis are used in [14]. The probabilistic models are employed to forecast the purchasing habits of customers. The research aimed at constructing a predictive model for customer buying behavior in the context of e-commerce. This research examined three product feature categories and established ways of identifying customer preferences for the three types of product features. If a product bought by a customer is

given to COREL, the software can offer the top n products it is likely to buy again in the future. Experiments on a real data set indicate that customer preference over product features is an important factor in decision-making, and COREL significantly outperforms the state-of-the-art methods. The paper [16] expanded the research in RFMT variables with T referring to time. It uses FF networks with tan-sigmoid transfer functions to predict patterns corresponding to RFMT of a customer. Finding a solution to traffic prediction and vehicle congestion is done in [17] which utilizes ant-based algorithm to solve vehicle congestion problems. ANNs are used in pistachio nuts classification [18] where an ANN is trained to analyze acoustic signals of pistachio nuts when impacted with steel plates. [19] expands the study of RNN in phenotype prediction which deals with biological data affected by ill-posed problems and missing data. It uses matrix factorization and RNN to predict sequences of phenotype and genotype imputation. In [20] the paper discusses about how deep learning models can achieve high levels of abstraction by which speech recognition, object detection, drug discovery etc. have improved

dramatically. Deep convolutional networks have revolutionized video, text, voice, and audio processing, while recurrent neural networks have excelled in speech and sequence recognition. This work presents an RNN model for predicting consumer behavior based on the R, F, M, and C variables which will first be computed using the existing dataset of customers and the customers will be segmented according to their R, F, M and C values and then input to the RNN and LSTM models.

Recurrent Neural Network Architecture

It is a slight variation on basic neural networks. In this form of network, the output from the previous phase is used as input for the following step. In classic neural networks, the inputs and outputs do not depend on one another temporally, but in scenarios where it is needed to predict the next occurrence in a sequence (for example, the next word of a sentence) there is a need to remember the previous occurrences. This is achieved by utilizing hidden layers inside the network, which aids in remembering information about a sequence as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Recurrent Neural Network

To train an RNN, we require both a training dataset and a separate test dataset. The sets are made up of input-label tuples, and the goal is to train the network with the training set before evaluating it with the test set. When training the network, the goal is to reduce the error between the input and label tuples. Equation 1 shows the loss function defines this error as follows:

$$\text{Loss function equation: } \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

*N represents the number of test samples.

Below Figure 2 shows the RNN architecture diagram of the research.

Figure 2: RNN architecture diagram

ReLU (Rectified Linear Units)

One major problem of Neural Networks is the vanishing gradient problem. This problem usually occurs if the neural network is a deep network. When propagating errors back to the initial layers, a series of matrix multiplication and chain rule result in the gradient being so small, it is up to the point of being vanished. Vanishing gradients make it difficult improve the cost function. ReLU is one proposed solution to this challenge. It also have significantly

better run times than the standard logistic function. Mathematically, it can be described as in Equation 2:

$$g(z) = \max \{0, z\} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where $g(z)$ is the ReLU function. The output of the ReLU function depends on the input. If input > 0 , the function outputs the input value, else 0 is output. Graphically it is represented as shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3: ReLU Graph

Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM)

The RNNs may suffer from a problem of short-term memory. LSTM are used to learn long dependencies between data, includes different gates which differentiate between what data to keep or forget, and

can pass down long chains of sequences to make predictions. Our model experimented with LSTM to find out whether it improves the accuracy of the model as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: LSTM Architecture

K-Fold Cross Validation

K-fold cross validation is a resampling technique used to assess machine learning models. It has a single parameter, k, which specifies how many groups a given data sample should be divided into. Cross validation is largely used in applied machine learning to measure the skill of a machine learning model using previously unseen data. It often produces less bias in model skill than other methods.

Algorithm used is:

- Randomly shuffle data
- Divide the data into k groups
- For each distinct group:

 - Use group as test dataset
 - Use remaining groups as training dataset
 - Fit model to training dataset
 - Assess it on test dataset
 - Save the evaluation score and delete model

- Summarize the model's skill based on the sample evaluation scores.

Proposed Model

Purchasing patterns of customers are recorded as transactions in the database of the store. The transactions happen temporally, so we can model this situation as a time-series problem. We compute our variables we will use which are the recency, frequency, monetary and clumpiness (RFMC) values of each individual consumer. After splitting the CLN into integers (to shape our vector into model understandable form) we place them in an array alongside the RFMC values. We then divide the data into train and test sets of which the last two weeks (Week 16 and Week 17) being the model's prediction. We train the RNN model for Weeks 0 to 15. We are using transactions in the first 15 weeks to use for predicting transactions within the last two weeks and matching customer IDs of customers in the training dataset, which are present in the test dataset. After running the model and computing accuracy and mean squared error, we compare the previous model with the new model as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Sample of shopper’s purchase behavior during different time interval

Model Description

We clean and adjust the raw dataset obtained from the store as weekly time intervals and set a lower and upper bound for the time intervals where transactions occur. The lower limit is the base time of our research and the upper limit is the finish time of our research about the behavior of the customer in the interval. Recency is calculated by comparing the lower limit time interval with the first immediate purchase. The frequency is the number of times a consumer makes a purchase during a given time period. Monetary value is calculated by summing the grand total prices of products that the customer purchased during this interval.

And finally, clumpiness is computed by Equation 3

$$C=1 + \frac{\log(xi/N) \cdot xi/N}{\log(n/N+1)} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

where xi is ith occurrence before last purchase, n is the number of events in the limit, while N is the entire time interval. At each time interval, the RFMC values are calculated for each client associated with a CLN. The model consists of three layers: the input layer, the hidden layer, and the output layer. Inputs are compressed for representation in the next layer. RFMC values of customers are input to the model

along with their respective CLN. The next time interval (t+1) is predicted and a loss value is computed is displayed graphically.

Experimental Setup

Hardware

Below is the list of hardware used during the creation of model:

- CPU: Core i5 2.30GHz
- GPU: Nvidia GeForce GTX 1050ti
- RAM: 8GB

Software

The software used in this project was Jupyter notebook (model), Python 3.8 and Anaconda terminal (for libraries).

Dataset

We used Ta-Feng grocery store dataset which was obtained from Kaggle. It has approximately 800,000 transactions for 32,000 users and 24,000 items. It has 4 months of customer data from November 2000 to February 2001. Below, a data dictionary is provided for details about the columns in Table 1:

Table 1: Data dictionary of the columns

Field Name	Data Type	Description	Example
TRANSACTION_DT	Date	Date of the transaction	11/13/2000
CUSTOMER_ID	Integer	Unique ID of customer	1069
AGE GROUP	String	Age group of customers	35-39
PIN_CODE	Integer	Customers PIN code	115
PRODUCT_SUBCLASS	Integer	Category of product	100205
PRODUCT_ID	Integer	Unique ID of a product	22000167620
AMOUNT	Integer	Quantity of bought product	2
ASSET	Integer	Items in stock	80
SALES_PRICE	Integer	Sales price of product	\$89.50

Hyperparameters

Table 2 below shows the hyperparameters with their settings values of this research.

S.no	Parameters	Settings
1	Epochs	1000
2	Hidden units	250
3	Time Interval	Weekly
4	Learning rate	0.001
5	Regularization coefficient	0.0001
6	Loss function	Mean Squared Error
7	Optimizer	Adam
8	Batch size	120
9	Validation Split	0.3
10	K-fold cross validation	K=10

Table 2: Hyperparameters with their settings values

Training graphs

Graphs of the research study are given below with the model accuracy graph and error graph.

Figure 6 below shows the Simple RNN (RFM) accuracy graph of the research.

MODEL ACCURACY GRAPH

Figure 6: SRNN (RFM) accuracy graph

Figure 7 below shows the LSTM (RFMC) with K-fold cross-validation accuracy graph of the research.

Figure 7: LSTM (RFMC) with F-fold cross validation accuracy graph

Explanation of graph

Variations as a result of batch training are not unusual. A perfect smooth loss graph/increased accuracy would be obtained if and only if the whole dataset is fed into the neural network, which is impossible.

ERROR GRAPH

Figure 8 below shows the Training Testing SRNN (RFM) error graph of the research.

Fig 8: Training Testing SRNN (RFM) error graph

Figure 9 below shows the train/test with LSTM-Kfold (RFMC) error graph of the research.

Figure 9: Train/test error graph for LSTM-Kfold (RFMC)

Sample Results (True and Predicted)

True value of RFMC variables for a customer with ID 00005241 is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: True value of RFMC variables of a customer

customer_id	frequency	recency	monetary	Clumpiness	
0	00005241	4	34	3396.0	7.873067

Predicted value of RFMC for a customer with ID 00005241 of next timestamp is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Predicted value of RFMC variables of a customer

ID	Frequency	Recency	Monetary	Clumpiness	
0	00005241	4.7746	28.1955	7975.07	7.44294

Results

The Table 5 below compares and summarizes the results we obtained from the experiments:

Models	Accuracy
RFM model (Simple RNN with ReLU)	74.6%
RFMC model (Simple RNN with ReLU)	84.1%
RFMC model (LSTM-RNN with ReLU and 10-folds cross validation)	85.2%

Table 5: Summary of the results

Discussion of Results

RNN models have good performance for RFMC prediction. RFMC model including clumpiness (84.1% accuracy) improves the accuracy of the model from a regular RFM model (74.6% accuracy) due to the presence of better features.

RFMC model with LSTM, ReLU activation and 10-fold cross validation provides slight improvements in accuracy (85.2%) than RFMC with Simple RNN and ReLU since LSTM tends to learn long term dependencies among the data and The k-fold cross validation technique divides the dataset randomly into k groups or folds of about equal pieces, reducing biasness and variance in the resultant estimate.

Conclusion and Potential Improvements

In this experiment we use RNN's to provide an improvement over the standard RFM model by introducing a new variable called clumpiness which indicates the customers who buy in bursts. This may provide a deeper knowledge and understanding of the customers buying behavior and devise new strategies to attract the target market. However, the proposed model has many other unexplored opportunities to improve even further. We can use more evidence and use features like gender, location, age, hobbies to develop a more insightful approach to the customer buying patterns and enhance our recommendation models.

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